

reduction) was measured and N₂-fixing blue-green algae (BGA) were counted 6, 41, 61, 84 and 98 days after transplanting (DT).

Seven core soil samples were taken randomly from each 1-m² plot by inserting 2-cm diameter, 12-cm-long glass tubes to about 5 cm below the soil surface. Tubes were plugged at the bottom and placed inside an airtight transparent cylinder, 7.2 cm in diameter and 32 cm long.

Incubation was in an atmosphere of 10% acetylene in air under sunlight (45-50 klux). A water bath maintained cylinder temperatures at 30-35°C. Ethylene produced after 15 minutes, 1 hour, and 3 hours incubation was determined by gas chromatography. The atmosphere of the cylinders was mixed before each sampling with a 50-ml syringe.

The same core samples were used to enumerate N₂-fixing BGA. Suspension dilutions of soil were plated on BG 11 medium without nitrogen.

Blooms of BGA appeared, but were not present in all replications of a given treatment at a given time. This agrees with results of acetylene reduction activity measurement, which varied widely between replications (see table). The small size of the plots, the irregular distribution of BGA in the fields, and the protection from inoculation by the water or the soil of the surrounding field by a continuous frame may not have permitted simultaneous growth of N₂-fixing BGA in the different replications of a treatment.

Plots in which straw was applied were

Acetylene reduction activity (ARA) present in paddy soil sampled at given days after transplanting (DT) of a rice crop at IRRI.^a

	ARA ^b (mmol C ₂ H ₄ /m ² per hour)					Av
	26 DT	41 DT ^c	61 DT	84 DT	98 DT ^d	
Control	32 a (80, 8, 8)	0 a (0, 0, 0)	115 a (60, 157, 128)	27 a (1, 80, 3)	113 a (4, 320, 13)	57
Straw applied	795 b (1224, 795, 366)	0 a (0, 0, 0)	65 a (20, 113, 8)	2a (6, 0, 0)	41 a (18, 3, 103)	180

^a Three hours incubation. ^b Figures in parentheses are replication values. Av values followed by common letter are not significantly different. ^c Measured 1 day after a heavy rain (80 mm). ^d Measured after harvest.

characterized by an earlier growth of N₂-fixing BGA and a significantly higher ARA at the beginning of the growth cycle of rice (see figure). The presence of photosynthetic bacteria was not measured.

The beneficial effect of surface application of straw on photosynthetic N₂-fixation may be due to an increase of CO₂ availability in the photic zone, a

decrease of mineral N and O₂ concentrations in the floodwater, and the provision of micro-aerobic microsites by the straw. Increased CO₂ availability and a low N concentration are known to favor the growth of N₂-fixing BGA. A low O₂ concentration and the micro-aerobic sites in the photic zone may have increased their specific nitrogen-fixing activity. ■

N₂-fixing BGA (no./cm²)

Evolution of the population of N₂-fixing BGA during a rice crop at IRRI.

Carryover effects of blue-green algae multiplication on subsequent direct-seeded paddy crop

S. Srinivasan, R. Anandan, and P. Narashimhan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Blue-green algae (BGA) seed production was undertaken at the state seed farm Kancheepuram during 1981 with four algal harvests from 25 April to 12 June. A demonstration followed to show farmers a crop grown without additional nitrogen on a plot where BGA had been

grown for seed.

Rice variety TKM9 was sown in 20 cm lines in the BGA 0.6-ha multiplication plot on 15 June. K₂O was applied at 60 kg P₂O₅/ha for algal seed multiplication, no phosphate fertilizer was applied. TKM9 was direct-seeded in a similar area with the normal application of 100-60-60 kg NPK/ha. Line spacing was maintained at 10 cm by thinning and gap filling 20 days after sowing. Both plots were harvested 20 September.

Results showed that even under direct seeding, a yield benefit equivalent to 100

Effect on rice yield of blue-green algae multiplication before the crop in Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)
Blue-green algae multiplication site (no N)	5.3
Standard (100 kg N/ha)	5.1

kg N/ha can be obtained in a crop grown in a plot where BGA was grown for more than 45 days (see table). This may be due to exudation of nitrogenous and other growth-promoting and growth-regulating substances during algal multiplication. ■